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Liquid air energy storage technology: a comprehensive review of research, development and deployment

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Keywords: liquid air energy storage, development status, dynamic modelling, economic modelling, applications through integration

Abstract

Liquid air energy storage (LAES) uses air as both the storage medium and working fluid, and it falls into the broad category of thermo-mechanical energy storage technologies. The LAES technology offers several advantages including high energy density and scalability, cost-competitiveness and non-geographical constraints, and hence has attracted a growing interest in recent years. As a result, several reviews have been published on the topic. However, these reviews covered little in the following aspects of LAES: dynamic simulation and optimisation, key components for LAES, LAES applications through integration, and unified economic and cost models for LAES. This article provides a comprehensive review on the LAES technology and fills the above gaps. Apart from applications in electrical grids such as peak-shaving, load shifting, and dealing with intermittency of renewable generation, the review also shows a diverse range of other LAES applications through integration, including waste heat and cold energy recovery and utilisation, multi-energy vector service provision, and sector coupling for chemical production and carbon capture. The review also leads to the recommendation of several areas for future research and development, including dynamic characteristics of whole LAES system integrated with renewables and end users; thermo-economic and dynamic optimization of stand-alone LAES and integrated systems; and experimental study on commercial systems.

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Abbreviations

ABC	Absorption chiller
A-CAES	Advanced compressed air energy storage
AIGV	Adjustable inlet guide vane
ASU	Air separation unit
AVD	Adjustable vanned diffuser
CAES	Compressed air energy storage
CDR	Carbon Dioxide Removal
CES	Cryogenic energy storage
CWHE	Coil-wound heat exchanger
C-ORC	Cryogenic Organic Rankine cycle
CAC	Carbon dioxide avoided cost
DPBP	Dynamic Payback period
FCI	Fixed capital investment
HEX	Heat exchanger
HTF	Heat transfer fluid
IGV	Inlet guide vane
IRR	Internal rate of return
KC	Kalina cycle
LAES	Liquid air energy storage
LCES	Liquid CO ₂ energy storage
LCOE	Levelized cost of energy
LCOS	Levelized cost of storage
LFU	Air liquefaction unit
LNG	Liquid natural gas
NE_RTE	Equivalent round trip efficiency
NG	Natural gas
NGCC	Natural gas combined cycle
NPV	Net present value
OMC	Operation and maintenance cost
ORC	Organic Rankine cycle
PBP	Payback period
PCM	Phase change material
PFHE	Plate fin heat exchanger
PHES	Pumped hydro energy storage
PRU	Power recovery unit
PTES	Pumped thermal energy storage
PV	Solar photovoltaics
ROI	Rate of return on investment
RTE	Round trip efficiency
SC-CAES	Supercritical CAES
SIR	Saving investment ratio
STOR	Short term operating reserve
SEC	Specific energy cost
SPC	Specific power cost
SPBP	Static Payback period
TEG	Thermo-electric generator
TES	Thermal energy storage

1. Introduction

Global transition to decarbonized energy systems by the middle of this century has different pathways, with the deep penetration of renewable energy sources and electrification being among the most popular ones [1, 2]. Due to the intermittency and fluctuation nature of renewable energy sources, energy storage is essential for coping with the supply-demand mismatches through smoothing the fluctuating generation, enabling energy arbitrage, mitigating renewable curtailment, and providing upward and downward flexibility [3]. This has led to a significant surge in the research and development of energy storage technologies over the last two decades. A wide range of energy storage technologies are now available at different development stages; see table 1 for a comparison of some major large-scale energy storage technologies. Among these technologies, PHES, and conventional CAES are regarded as mature technologies for large-scale and medium-to-long-duration storage applications, and have been deployed commercially at a relatively low cost [4]. But they have a very low energy density and are constrained by topological and geological conditions. Electrochemical energy storage, particularly Li-ion and sodium ion batteries, are mainly for

Table 1. Comparison of technical characteristics of energy storage systems for large-scale application.

Storage method	Energy storage density (Wh L ⁻¹)	Power rating	Discharge time	Round trip efficiency	Lifetime (year)	Response time	Daily self-discharge	Geological conditions	Maturity [11]
LAES	60–200 [12, 13]	100 kW–Up to GW [12, 14]	Hours–days [15]	50%–70% [15]	> 30 [14]	min [16, 17]	~0.5%–1% [12]	No	Pre-commercialized—Commercialized
PHS	0.2–2 [18, 19]	100–5000 MW [12, 15]	Hours–days [12, 20]	60%–80% [12, 20]	30–50 [21]	min [19]	~0 [22]	Strict	Commercialized
CAES	0.4–20 [18, 19]	5–300 MW [12, 20]	Hours–days [12, 20]	41%–75% [19]	20–40 [12]	min [19]	~0 [22]	Strict	Commercialized
Flow battery (Vanadium redox)	10–70 [18, 19]	Up to 200 MW [23]	Seconds–10 h [15, 20]	60%–90% [15, 19]	5–20 [20]	< sec [19]	0.15%–0.2% [20, 24]	No	Commercialized
Hydrogen storage coupled with fuel cell	500–3000 [12] 600 (20 MPa) [19]	0.1–50 MW [15, 21]	Seconds–days [12, 15] Hours–weeks [19]	20%–50% [21, 25]	10–30 [19]	< sec [20] sec–min [19]	~0 [22]	No	Pre-commercialized

small-to-medium scale, high-power, fast-response and mobile applications [5]. This work is concerned with LAES, which is a thermo-mechanical energy storage technology, and an alternative to PHES and conventional CAES technologies. Such a technology has several key advantages including high scalability, no geographical/geological constraints, cost-effectiveness, and multi-vector energy service provision [6]. As a result, recent years have seen a growing interest in the LAES technology.

1.1. The LAES development history

The pioneering work on LAES can be dated back to 1977 when liquid air was proposed for peak-shaving of power grids by University of Newcastle upon Tyne [7]. This led to subsequent research by Hitachi in 1980–1990s and Mitsubishi Heavy Industries, aiming at replacing CAES in the late 1990s [8]. It was a collaborative research between the University of Leeds and Highview Enterprises Ltd (now branded as Highview Power) started from around 2005, which has led to substantial development of the technology — the world’s first LAES pilot plant (350 kW/2.5 MWh) between 2009 and 2012 (figure 1(a)) [9]; a pre-commercial LAES plant (5 MW/15 MWh) between 2018 and 2020 (figure 1(b)); and the announcement of the construction of the world’s first commercial LAES plant (50 MW/250 MWh) in 2020 [10]. The first commercial plant is still under construction and is projected to be operational in late 2023 or early 2024, and the actual scale of the plant has been increased from 250 MWh to 300 MWh.

1.2. Previous reviews on LAES

Several review articles on LAES have been published in recent years. They are summarised as follows:

- Lim *et al* [28] provided the first review related to LAES in 2016, which focused on the so-called liquid air economy in Malaysia, including liquid air engine, cold energy provision, back-up power generation, and renewable firming.
- Borri *et al* [29] reviewed the status of scientific research on LAES up to 2019, which included the number of publications, and research institutions and their key research focuses.
- Damak *et al* [30] published a review on LAES research up to 2019. This article covered the basic LAES system, the integrated systems, and the related challenges, and concluded that experimental validation of theoretical performance, new applications and detailed economic evaluation were highly needed for LAES.
- O’Callaghan *et al* [31] provided a review of LAES research up to 2020, including specifically high-grade cold storage, and integration of LAES with LNG, ASU, and nuclear power plants etc. The review highlighted the needs for economic comparison between different LAES integrated systems and the associated dynamic analyses.
- Another review led by Borri *et al* [32] was published in 2021, covering the status of LAES research up to 2020, and including techno-economic performance of stand-alone, hybrid, and poly-generation LAES systems. The lack of studies on small-scale LAES and dynamic behaviour of LAES was highlighted.
- Vecchi *et al* [6] led a LAES review published in 2021, covering the state-of-the-art work related to LAES up to 2020, and including the detailed techno-economic assessment, cross-comparison between stand-alone and hybrid LAES systems, and different LAES system integration and applications. They highlighted the needs

for more work on realistic and extensive integration models and systems, with the multi-vector operation of LAES concluded as the most promising integration pathway.

1.3. Novelty of this review

The summary of the literature reviews in section 1.2 above suggest the following gaps in LAES research and developments:

- Dynamic modelling and optimisation of LAES have not been reviewed so far;
- Little has been covered on key components that have been or could potentially be applied in LAES;
- Some highly promising integrated LAES systems with renewables have not been included so far;
- Unified economic models and component cost models have not been included in the previous reviews.

This review will cover all the above. It is organised in the following manner. First, the fundamentals of LAES are briefly outlined in section 2, followed by components and system modelling in section 3. Techno-economic analyses of both standalone and hybrid LAES systems are summarised in section 4. Potential applications through integration are given in section 5. Finally, section 6 concludes the review with main conclusions.

2. Fundamentals of LAES

2.1. Working principle

A stand-alone LAES normally has three key subsystems, namely an air liquefaction unit (LFU) for charging, a storage subsystem, and a power recovery unit (PRU) for discharging, as illustrated in figure 2. The storage subsystem consists of three stores, one for liquid air (main store), one for compression heat and one for high-grade cold energy. A detailed working principle is summarized in the following:

- *LAES charging process* The LFU uses off-peak (low-cost) electricity or renewable power to compress purified air to a high pressure (charging pressure) through multistage compression (state 1–2), which is then cooled in HEXs ('cold box', state 2–3) by recirculating air between the cold box and the cold store. Finally, liquid air is produced by expansion machines, such as a cryo-turbine or a Joule–Thomson throttling valve (state 4–5) and stored in a liquid air store (tank) at ~ 78 K and near-ambient pressure (state 5–6). In the meantime, the compression heat is recovered and stored in the compression heat store.
- *LAES discharging process* The stored liquid air is first pumped to a higher pressure (discharging pressure, state 6–7), with the cold energy harvested and stored in the cold store (state 7–8). The stored cold energy is reused in the LFU to improve the liquid air yield and increase energy efficiency. The high-pressure air is then heated by the environmental heat first before superheated by stored compression heat, and finally expanding in an air turbine train to generate electricity (state 8–9).

Clearly, efficient liquefaction and power recovery processes can significantly enhance the working performance of the overall system. Thus, the key technologies for the two processes are discussed in sections 2.2 and 2.3, respectively.

2.2. Air liquefaction

The air liquefaction process turns the high-pressure air into liquid at a suitable pressure (boiling point at -194.35 °C/78.8 K at 1 bar). This significantly reduces the volume by ~ 700 times [34]. Key parameters affecting the performance of the liquefaction process and liquid air yield include the type of liquefaction cycle used, the charging pressure, the performance of multi-stream heat exchangers (HEXs) (cold box), compressors and the cryo-turbine etc. The optimal charging pressure has been investigated in several studies, which has been shown to be at around 12–18 MPa [35–38]. It has also been found that, the higher the efficiencies of the compressors and cryo-turbine, the better the liquefaction performance, with the impact of the compressor efficiency stronger than that of the cryo-turbine [39]. The role of the HEX efficiency is also crucial, as illustrated by Guizzi *et al* [35], who showed that an increase of 5 K in the pinch point of the 'cold box' could lead to a 2.2% of decrease in RTE.

Commonly used air liquefaction cycles include Linde–Hampson cycle, Claude cycle, Kapitza cycle, Heylandt cycle, and Collins cycle [34] as illustrated in figure 3. The Linde–Hampson cycle has the simplest configuration (figure 3(a)), featured by a long lifespan and a low cost. However, the exergy loss of the irreversible throttling process and the mismatch of the temperature profile in the cold box mean a low exergy efficiency of the cycle below $\sim 10\%$ [40]. The Claude cycle (figure 3(b)), Kapitza cycle (figure 3(c)), Heylandt cycle (figure 3(d)) and Collins cycle (figure 3(e)) are variants of the Linde–Hampson cycle, aimed for

improving the liquid yield. The Claude cycle uses two expanding machines, they are a Joule Thomson valve and an expander, which has been shown to have a comparable efficiency but a better economics than Collins cycle [41]. However, the Collins cycle allows the system to work under a lower pressure. The disadvantages of Collins cycle are its complexity in system configuration, and high investment and maintenance costs due to multiple cryogenic expansion devices. Borri *et al* [42] and Zhang *et al* [43] investigated a LAES system with a Kapitza cycle, showed that the cycle was more suitable for low-pressure working conditions. The Heylandt cycle is a high-pressure cycle (up to 20 MPa) [34]. Hamdy *et al* [44] compared the performance of six

Figure 4. Common power recovery cycles of cryogen energy: (a) direct expansion cycle; (b) direct expansion with Rankine cycle; (c) direct expansion with Brayton cycle; (d) combined cycle. Reprinted from [26], Copyright (2022), with permission from Elsevier.

liquefaction processes. They found that the Claude cycle had the highest exergy efficiency of $\sim 76\%$ – 82% ; whereas the Heylandt cycle gave the highest RTE with the lowest liquefaction power requirement, and the Kapitza cycle could achieve the lowest investment costs.

2.3. Power recovery

The power recovery process extracts the cryogenic exergy in the stored liquid air and converts it back into electrical power when in demand, with the stored compression heat reused in the process. Key factors affecting the performance of the power recovery process include the discharging pressure, the cold recovery process in the evaporator, the reheating temperature before expansion, and the efficiencies of the cryo-pump and turbines. Studies of the effect of the discharging pressure have indicated an optimal operating pressure of ~ 9 – 12 MPa [45, 46]. However, this optimal value varies depending on the system configuration and other operating conditions [47, 48]. Tafone *et al* demonstrated that a 1% of increase in the reheating temperature could produce a 1% of increase in the specific work output when the discharging pressure remains constant [48]; whereas Liang *et al* [47] found that the turbine efficiency has the most important impact on the overall system efficiency with the effect of cryo-pump efficiency being lowest. Sciacovelli *et al* [37] demonstrated that a 16% of enhancement in recoverable cold energy could lead to a 20% and 30% of increase in the RTE and the liquid yield, respectively.

There are four basic cycles for power recovery (electrical generation): direct expansion cycle, Rankine cycle, Brayton cycle, and combined cycle [26]; see figure 4 for schematic illustrations. For a standalone LAES system, the commonly adopted cycle is the direct expansion. In such a cycle, liquid air is pumped to a high pressure, and then heated before expanding in the turbines to generate power. It has the lowest cryogenic exergy utilization rate, because only the mechanical (pressure) part of the cryogenic exergy is used. The recovery and reuse of the thermal part of the cryogenic exergy are crucial, which, as briefly discussed in section 2.1, can be stored in the high-grade cold store, and reused in the liquefaction process to enhance the liquid yield [49]. In fact, the use of a direct expansion cycle with high-grade cold recovery in the discharging process could lead to a much higher RTE than only a combined cycle is used [50]. In addition, as reported by Peng *et al* [36], some 20%–45% of the compression heat could be in excess and utilised through integration with other processes to improve the overall system efficiency. Examples of such integration include

LAES-ORC [38], LAES-ORC- Vapor Compression Refrigeration Cycle (VCRC) [42] and LAES-ORC-ARC [51].

2.4. Basic concepts and definitions

Several concepts and terminologies have been used in this paper and they are defined as follows.

- Work input/consumption: net electrical power consumed by air compressors and cryogenic pump.
- Work output: net electrical power produced by air turbines and cryogenic turbines.
- Isentropic efficiency: ratio of actual power of a device to power consumed/produced during an isentropic process.
- Heat transfer effectiveness: ratio of actual heat transfer rate to the maximum possible heat transfer rate.
- RTE: ratio of total net power output to total net power input of a stand-alone LAES system; or ratio of total net power output to total electrical, cooling and heating power inputs of an integrated LAES system; more details are provided in table 2.
- Exergy destruction: exergy destroyed over an irreversible process due to for example loss of heat to the environment.
- Exergy efficiency: ratio of total exergy output to total exergy input of a system or a component; see table 2 for details.
- Electrical storage efficiency: for a stand-alone LAES system, the electrical storage efficiency has the same definition as the RTE, but for an integrated LAES system, electric storage efficiency is the ratio of electrical power output to the electrical power input of the system.

3. LAES components and system modelling

This section covers studies at both component and system levels. It starts from the component level in sections 3.1 and 3.2, where progresses and current focuses are summarised. This is followed by the detailed static and dynamic modelling methods in section 3.3. Finally, economic modelling of LAES systems is presented in section 3.4.

3.1. Components for the charging process

3.1.1. Air compressors

Little work has been found in the literature on air compressors specifically for LAES. However, air compression technologies used in CAES systems are similar to those in LAES systems, and as a result, this review includes the work on air compressors for CAES systems. Due to large exergy loss during compression, load fluctuations, environmental factors, and system performance characteristics, air compressors for LAES, and indeed for SC-CAES systems, need to have a high off-design efficiency, a large pressure ratio, a good inter-stage heat recovery efficiency, and a wide operation range under off-design conditions [52].

Studies on air compressors have focused on design methods, internal flow characteristics, energy loss mechanisms, impacts of off-design operations, and control methods. Commonly used compressors include centrifugal, axial, reciprocating, and scroll types [53]. Liang *et al* [39] showed that the system RTE could be enhanced by 15.7% if the isentropic efficiency of compressors could be improved from 80% to 95%. Tafone *et al* [54] highlighted a negative impact of low turbomachinery isentropic efficiency on the system RTE under off-design conditions, which could be amplified by inappropriate charging pressures. Zhou *et al* [55] proposed a concept of synergy analysis for studying the relationship between flow separation, heat transfer and losses due to turbomachinery rotors, which could be used to optimise the blade profile to improve the performance. Lin *et al* experimentally studied the coupled characteristics of the compressor [56] and the flow behaviour in the impeller backside cavity under different AVD angles [57]. Guo *et al* [58] established a model for a multi-stage compression process under off-design conditions for CAES systems, and an optimal adjustment method for IGV angles. They showed that the combination of AIGVs and AVDs was a more suitable method to extend the operating range of centrifugal compressors [59], which could increase the pressure ratio range by 232.5%. Salvini *et al* [60] proposed a two compressor capacity control method for a small-scale CAES system with multi-stage reciprocating compressors. Their control system could be used to adjust the absorbed power, minimize the specific compression work and increase the system flexibility. Clearly, more work is needed to develop a control strategy for compressors to cope with both the varying renewable power supply and varying end use demand.

3.1.2. Cryogenic expander

The use of a cryogenic liquid expander to replace the throttle valve could lead to a higher liquefaction yield and a greater LAES system efficiency [59]. The commonly used cryogenic expanders include reciprocating

type, radial inflow or mixed flow turbines [61]. However, only several studies can be found on the area. Examples include optimal design methods, strength analysis and cryogenic cavitation simulation by Song *et al* [62]; and experimental measurements of performance of a cryogenic liquid turbine in a closed-loop liquid nitrogen (LN₂) system by Wang *et al* [63] who found that the peak isentropic efficiency of the turbine was 78.8%. Li *et al* reported a design and model test method for a liquid turbine of an SC-CAES system [64] with the experimental performance of the turbine tested with water. Their results showed a maximum efficiency of 75.16% at the rated conditions [65]. Kaupert *et al* [66] demonstrated that the performance, erosion, and vibration of liquid expanders could be improved by changing the type of expander from radial inflow centrifugal to axial impulse, with the expander power output varying from 20 kW to 2 MW. Kimmel and Cathery [67] proposed a design of a two-phase expander made from cryogenic aluminium alloy, and showed that the use of a special jet exducer with a condensation cone could improve the expansion efficiency, the shaft torque and the shaft power.

3.1.3. Multi-stream HEXs

Cryogenic multi-stream HEXs are critical components of the LAES system for recovering cold energy during discharging and liquefying air during charging. The compressor power consumption could be reduced by 5% with a 1% of increase in the heat transfer effectiveness of the HEXs [35]. Liang *et al* [26] investigated the effect of pinch point of HEXs on the LAES performance, and found that the performance is mostly affected by cryogenic evaporator and the multi-stream cold boxes. The pinch points of these HEXs were recommended to be below 10 K to ensure a high system RTE. However, a lower temperature difference can lead to the needs for a higher heat transfer area and hence a bulky equipment with a high capital cost. Hamdy *et al* [68] ranked the capital cost of the cold box as the second most expensive component in their economic analysis.

Two major types of cryogenic HEXs are commonly used, a CWHE and a PFHE [69]. Spiral wound tubes are used in the CWHEs, which make them capable of withstanding thermal shocks, thus enabling a quick start-up and an efficient transient operation [70]. But they are expensive to manufacture, and hence are more suitable for small to medium scale applications [69]. The PFHEs are featured by high thermal conductivity and high mechanical strength at low temperatures [71], and have therefore been used in both the pilot and pre-commercial LAES plants.

There have been various publications on modelling the HEXs applicable to LAES. For example, Popov *et al* reviewed cryogenic HEXs [70], which covered modelling methods in a comprehensive manner; whereas Vecchi *et al* [72] and Sciacovelli *et al* [37] applied the so-called ϵ -NTU method to model HEXs for LAES. Gupta *et al* contributed to the development of design and optimization models for the HEXs by improving the heat transfer correlations [71] and geometrical configuration [73], who also set up test rigs for helium-based cryogenic CWHE [74]. Wang *et al* developed a graph-based model [75] and a simulation tool [76] for cryogenic heat transfer. Skaugen *et al* [77] developed a distributed parameter model for PFHE to predict the HEX performance, and showed an accuracy comparable to that of Aspen HYSYS software package. Peng *et al* developed a particle swarm optimization algorithm for sizing PFHEs based on a log-mean temperature difference model, aimed to minimize the weight, annual cost and passage arrangement under multiple operating conditions [78] and inlet flow mal-distribution [79].

3.1.4. Thermal energy stores and storage media

Numerous studies can be found in the literature on thermal energy storage materials, devices, and system integration, but not all are suitable for LAES.

- *Compression heat store and storage media* Water, thermal oil and solid particulate are among the main TES materials for storing compression heat. Water is the most used material for TES below ~ 200 °C and has the advantages of high specific heat, good heat transfer properties, excellent chemical compatibilities, and extremely low cost. It has therefore been used in harvesting and storing compression heat from multi-stage compressors [80]. Spherical and barrel shaped vessels are popular designs for water-based TES devices [81]. Thermal oils are another commonly used TES material for compression heat storage. Such type of materials can be used at a much higher temperature (up to ~ 400 °C) than water, and a two-tank configuration is often used as the TES device design [35]. Thermal oils have a lower vapour pressure compared with water at elevated temperatures but are expensive and flammable. Solid particles as TES materials have been studied extensively, and TES devices using this type of materials are called packed beds. Such TES devices can use air [82] or thermal oil [83] as HTF. Xie *et al* proposed a spray-type packed-bed TES concept with a liquid flowing through packed particles in the form of a film driven by gravity [84] and experimentally studied such a design [85].

- *High-grade cold store and storage media* As indicated earlier, high-grade cold storage is among the most effective ways to enhance the RTE of LAES. Morgan *et al* [86] found that an increase in the portion of the recycled cold energy from 51% to 91% could increase the RTE from 8% to ~50%. Different cold storage materials have been proposed. They can be classified into two categories of liquid-based and solid-based materials. The liquid-based materials include methanol, propane, R218, R123 [50, 87, 88]; whereas quartzite rocks and gravel are examples of the solid-based cold storage materials [37, 87, 89]. The liquid-based cold storage materials have a high specific heat and are easy to control both the temperature and the heat transfer, but are flammable and expensive. The solid-based cold storage materials are cheaper and safer but are not easy to control the temperature and heat transfer. Due to these different characteristics, the storage device designs differ. The two-tank configuration is often used for liquid-based storage media, such as a methanol and propane [87], methanol and R218 [50], and R123 and propane [88]; whereas the packed-bed configuration is often the choice for solid-based storage media. The LAES pilot and pre-commercial plants used solid-based packed-bed store. A brief summary of the literature on this area is therefore given here. Hüttermann and Span [89] highlighted the significant effect of temperature-dependence of the specific heat capacity of solid materials on the performance of the packed bed. Chai *et al* [90] and Liao *et al* [91] studied packed-bed based cryogenic energy storage both experimentally and numerically under super-critical (SC) conditions. They found that the exergy loss of direct heat transfer within the packed-bed was smaller than that of indirect multi-tank storage configurations [89]. Sciacovelli *et al* [37] numerically studied the dynamic characteristics of a 100 MW/300 MWh LAES system with a packed-bed cold store. They found that the RTE decreased by 12.6% compared with that under nominal conditions due to the formation of thermocline, this effect could be eliminated by multiple charging/discharging cycles. Lin *et al* [92] proposed a cascaded packed-bed cryogenic storage configuration, and found that a high RTE of LAES up to 65% could be achieved.

3.2. Components for the discharging process

3.2.1. Air turbines

Similar to air compressors, air turbines have a significant impact on the LAES system efficiency [58]. Such a turbine uses similar technologies as the A-CAES systems. Liang *et al* [26] showed that the RTE of LAES could be enhanced remarkably by 19.7% if the turbine efficiency is increased from 80% to 95%.

Many studies have been performed on the aerodynamics and internal flow characteristics of air turbines, aimed for solutions to flow loss reduction and efficiency improvement. Zhang *et al* [93, 94] investigated a four-stage radial inflow turbine (figure 5(a)), of the world-first 1.5 MW S-CAES system. Li *et al* [65] and Wang *et al* [95] studied the overall internal flow characteristics of turbines under variable operating conditions. Their results indicated that the ideal gas model could not even qualitatively describe the real flow pattern under SC conditions. Wang *et al* [96] also investigated the internal flow characteristics of a four-stage axial turbine for a new 10 MW CAES system with compact chamber and short diffuser (figure 5(b)).

Significant progress has been made in the study of leakage flow in case-shroud clearance [99], tip clearance [100] and back cavity effects on efficiency [101] of air turbines. These studies have led to the following observations:

- The labyrinth seal flow has been found to have a negligible effect on rotor main flow, while its effect on the leakage flow is significant [100].
- A concept termed ‘physical quantity synergy’ has been employed to analyse the shroud cavity flow [97], leading to the recommendation of a dimensionless seal clearance of below 1.5%.
- The rotor geometry has an effect on the tip leakage flow. A new blade with an optimal NACA-based profile has been proposed [96], which not only increases the isentropic efficiency by over 1%, but also meets the deformation and structure strength requirements.
- The clearance erosion caused by sand particles in air radial turbines has been addressed by Wang *et al* [102].
- The effect of chamber roughness on aerodynamics turbines has been investigated (for the first time), and its effect on internal flow loss has also been analysed [103].

3.2.2. Cryogenic pumps

Cryogenic pumps are used for elevating liquid air pressure during discharging, which should be able to withstand and operate in extremely cold environment. They can be grouped into bath cryo-pumps, refrigerator-cooled cryo-pumps and helium-cooled cryo-pumps categories [104]. There have been very few studies focusing on cryogenic pumps for LAES, which may be due to the minor effect of cryogenic pump efficiency on the RTE of LAES systems. The isentropic efficiency of the cryogenic pumps is often set at 0.75 or 0.7 in most thermodynamics studies [33, 43, 100]. The changes in the efficiency do not affect much the

Figure 5. Photos of (a) A four-stage radial turbine system of the first 1.5 MW SCAES system. Republished with permission of ASME, from [97]; permission conveyed through Copyright Clearance Center, Inc. and (b) an axial turbine system of a 10 MW CAES system. Reprinted from [98], Copyright (2020), with permission from Elsevier.

LAES performance. For example, Guo *et al* [105] found that the LAES system RTE only increases by 1% with an increase of 4% in cryogenic pump efficiency; whereas Liang *et al* [26] showed that there is only 1.4% of RTE increase when the pump efficiency is increased from 70% to 85%. An important area of research related to cryo-pumps, which is worth to note, is the cavitation behaviour during pumping liquid nitrogen [106], liquid oxygen [107], and LNG [108], which could lead to practical operation problems.

3.3. LAES system-scale modelling

3.3.1. Static modelling

Static modelling of LAES systems includes mainly the energy and exergy analyses. The energy analysis is based on the first law of thermodynamics for maximising the thermal efficiency [33, 34]. The exergy analysis uses the second law of thermodynamics for reducing irreversibilities [35, 36]. The purposes of the modelling are to investigate how cycle parameters, such as operating temperatures and pressures, affect the cycle performance, and to identify optimal cycles through parametric and optimisation studies. Table 2 provides a summary of the methods, with the thermodynamic models for the design and off-design conditions given separately.

3.3.2. Dynamic modelling

Although a complete LAES plant involves complex liquefaction process, multi-stream HEXs and operations under SC conditions, most reported studies have been focusing on steady-state simulation and analyses. These steady-state assumptions often deviate from actual situations, particularly during start-up, shut-down, and load-following (a key function for storage) periods, dynamic simulation is essential to ensure correct designs, realistic system-level performance prediction for economic analyses, and safe and smooth operations of real-world LAES systems.

Several studies have been found in the literature on the transient behaviour of packed-bed thermal stores for LAES plants [37, 83, 104, 105, 109], but the modelling of other components are under the steady-state conditions. Sciacovelli *et al* [37] showed that the specific liquefaction work could be increased by $\sim 25\%$ by altering the cold end temperature of the cold box, but the transient behaviour of the packed bed has no significant effect on the specific work output of the expansion process. They also observed a change of the RTE from cycle to cycle, and eventually reached $\sim 48\%$ after 20 cycles upon the establishment of a cyclic-steady-state operation of the packed bed. Legrand *et al* [110] investigated the effect of the transient behaviour of a cold storage packed bed on the liquid yield and pressure drop of a LAES system. Their results indicated that the liquid yield ratio decreased dramatically but the pressure drop increased by 1.8 times after 6 \sim 8 h of charging. Guo *et al* [111] investigated the dynamic characteristics of a two-stage packed-bed of a LAES system over multiple cycles. They considered the storage period between the charging and discharging processes, as well as cold energy loss. Their results indicated a RTE of LAES at 16.8%, which was lower than that of an ideal cycle. Wang *et al* [83] studied the effects of dynamic performance of both heat and cold packed-bed stores on LAES system performance over both the start-up and steady-state operation periods. Their results showed an average liquid air yield increasing from 23% (at the start-up) to 56% (at the steady

Table 2. Static modelling methods of LAES system.

Components	Energy analysis modelling	Exergy analysis modelling	Notes
Thermodynamic law	<p>The 1st thermodynamic law: $Q - W = \sum_i q_{mi} (h_0 - h_i)$</p> <p>Design conditions: $\dot{W}_{ci} = q_m (h_{i+1} - h_i)$ [38] or $\dot{W}_{ci} = q_m C_p T_{c,in,i} \frac{\beta_{c,ct}^{k-1} - 1}{\beta_{c,ct} - 1} \eta_{ci}$ [117], Off-design conditions [118, 119]: $\beta_{c,i} = z_1 \dot{G}_c^2 + z_2 \dot{G}_c + z_3$, $\eta_c = \left[1 - z_4 (1 - \dot{h}_c)^2 \right] \left(\frac{\dot{h}_c}{\dot{G}_c} \right) \left(2 - \left(\frac{\dot{h}_c}{\dot{G}_c} \right) \right)$,</p>	<p>The 2nd thermodynamic law [26]: $0 = \sum \left(1 - \frac{T_0}{T_k} \right) \dot{Q}_k - W_{cv} + \sum q_{mi} e_i - \sum q_{mj} e_j - E_d e_i = h_i - h_0 - T_0 (s_i - s_0) + 0.5 v_i^2 + g z_i$</p> <p>Isobaric compression: $E_{d,c} = W_{cv,c} + q_m (e_{in,c} - e_{o,c})$ $e_{i,t} = h_{i,t} - h_0 - T_0 (s_{i,t} - s_0) e_{j,t} = h_{o,t} - h_0 - T_0 (s_{j,t} - s_0)$</p>	<p>Symbols: \dot{Q}—heat power, \dot{W}—electric power, q_m—mass flow rate, h—enthalpy, E_d—exergy destruction Subscripts: i—inlet, j—outlet, cv—control volume, k—component</p> <p>Symbols: C_p—specific heat, T—temperature, β_c—compression ratio, k—adiabatic index, η—efficiency, \dot{G}_c—reduced mass flow rate, \dot{h}_c—reduced speed, $z_1 \sim z_4$—constants Subscripts: c—compressor</p>
Compressor	<p>Design conditions: $\dot{W}_{ti} = q_m (h_{i+1} - h_i)$ [38] or $\dot{W}_{ti} = \eta_{ti} q_m C_p T_{i,in,i} \left(1 - \beta_{t,t}^{\frac{k-1}{k}} \right)$ [117], Off-design conditions [118, 119]: $\frac{\dot{h}_t}{\eta_{to}} = \left[1 - z_5 (1 - \dot{h}_t)^2 \right] \left(\frac{\dot{h}_t}{\dot{G}_t} \right) \left(2 - \left(\frac{\dot{h}_t}{\dot{G}_t} \right) \right)$, $\frac{q_m}{q_{m0}} = \frac{\sqrt{T_{0,in}/T_{0,in}}}{\sqrt{(\beta_t^2 - 1)/(\beta_{to}^2 - 1)}}$</p>	<p>The 2nd thermodynamic law [26]: $0 = \sum \left(1 - \frac{T_0}{T_k} \right) \dot{Q}_k - W_{cv} + \sum q_{mi} e_i - \sum q_{mj} e_j - E_d e_i = h_i - h_0 - T_0 (s_i - s_0) + 0.5 v_i^2 + g z_i$</p> <p>Isobaric compression: $E_{d,c} = W_{cv,c} + q_m (e_{in,c} - e_{o,c})$ $e_{i,t} = h_{i,t} - h_0 - T_0 (s_{i,t} - s_0) e_{j,t} = h_{o,t} - h_0 - T_0 (s_{j,t} - s_0)$</p>	<p>Symbols: \dot{Q}—heat power, \dot{W}—electric power, q_m—mass flow rate, h—enthalpy, E_d—exergy destruction Subscripts: i—inlet, j—outlet, cv—control volume, k—component</p> <p>Symbols: C_p—specific heat, T—temperature, β_c—compression ratio, k—adiabatic index, η—efficiency, \dot{G}_c—reduced mass flow rate, \dot{h}_c—reduced speed, $z_1 \sim z_4$—constants Subscripts: c—compressor</p>
Turbine	<p>Design conditions: $\dot{W}_{ti} = q_m (h_{i+1} - h_i)$ [38] or $\dot{W}_{ti} = \eta_{ti} q_m C_p T_{i,in,i} \left(1 - \beta_{t,t}^{\frac{k-1}{k}} \right)$ [117], Off-design conditions [118, 119]: $\frac{\dot{h}_t}{\eta_{to}} = \left[1 - z_5 (1 - \dot{h}_t)^2 \right] \left(\frac{\dot{h}_t}{\dot{G}_t} \right) \left(2 - \left(\frac{\dot{h}_t}{\dot{G}_t} \right) \right)$, $\frac{q_m}{q_{m0}} = \frac{\sqrt{T_{0,in}/T_{0,in}}}{\sqrt{(\beta_t^2 - 1)/(\beta_{to}^2 - 1)}}$</p>	<p>The 2nd thermodynamic law [26]: $0 = \sum \left(1 - \frac{T_0}{T_k} \right) \dot{Q}_k - W_{cv} + \sum q_{mi} e_i - \sum q_{mj} e_j - E_d e_i = h_i - h_0 - T_0 (s_i - s_0) + 0.5 v_i^2 + g z_i$</p> <p>Isobaric compression: $E_{d,c} = W_{cv,c} + q_m (e_{in,c} - e_{o,c})$ $e_{i,t} = h_{i,t} - h_0 - T_0 (s_{i,t} - s_0) e_{j,t} = h_{o,t} - h_0 - T_0 (s_{j,t} - s_0)$</p>	<p>Symbols: e—exergy, s—entropy, β_t—expansion ratio, z_5—constant Subscripts: t—turbine, o—the reference state</p>
Pump	<p>Design conditions: $\dot{W}_p = q_m (h_{p,o} - h_{p,i})$ Off-design conditions [72, 120]: $\frac{q_m}{q_{m0}} = \frac{N}{N_0}$, $\frac{\Delta P}{\Delta P_0} = \left(\frac{N}{N_0} \right)^2$</p>	<p>The 2nd thermodynamic law [26]: $0 = \sum \left(1 - \frac{T_0}{T_k} \right) \dot{Q}_k - W_{cv} + \sum q_{mi} e_i - \sum q_{mj} e_j - E_d e_i = h_i - h_0 - T_0 (s_i - s_0) + 0.5 v_i^2 + g z_i$</p> <p>Isobaric compression: $E_{d,c} = W_{cv,c} + q_m (e_{in,c} - e_{o,c})$ $e_{i,t} = h_{i,t} - h_0 - T_0 (s_{i,t} - s_0) e_{j,t} = h_{o,t} - h_0 - T_0 (s_{j,t} - s_0)$</p>	<p>Symbols: ΔP—pump heat, N—motor speed Subscripts: p—pump</p>
Cryo-expander	<p>Design conditions: $\dot{W}_{ct} = q_m (h_{ct,j} - h_{ct,o})$ Off-design conditions [118, 119]: $\frac{\dot{h}_{ct}}{\eta_{to}} = \left[1 - z_6 (1 - \dot{h}_{ct})^2 \right] \left(\frac{\dot{h}_{ct}}{\dot{G}_{ct}} \right) \left(2 - \left(\frac{\dot{h}_{ct}}{\dot{G}_{ct}} \right) \right)$,</p>	<p>The 2nd thermodynamic law [26]: $0 = \sum \left(1 - \frac{T_0}{T_k} \right) \dot{Q}_k - W_{cv} + \sum q_{mi} e_i - \sum q_{mj} e_j - E_d e_i = h_i - h_0 - T_0 (s_i - s_0) + 0.5 v_i^2 + g z_i$</p> <p>Isobaric compression: $E_{d,c} = W_{cv,c} + q_m (e_{in,c} - e_{o,c})$ $e_{i,t} = h_{i,t} - h_0 - T_0 (s_{i,t} - s_0) e_{j,t} = h_{o,t} - h_0 - T_0 (s_{j,t} - s_0)$</p>	<p>Symbols: ct—cryo-turbine, Symbols: z_6—constant</p>

(Continued.)

Table 2. (Continued.)

Components	Energy analysis modelling	Exergy analysis modelling	Notes
Heat exchanger	<p>Design conditions: $\dot{Q}_{hex} = q_m (h_{hex,o} - h_{hex,i})$ Off-design conditions [72]: $UA = UA_0 \left(\frac{q_m}{q_{mo}} \right)^{0.8}$</p>	$E_{d,hex} = \sum \left(1 - \frac{T_0}{T_k} \right) \dot{Q}_k + \sum q_{m,i} e_i - \sum q_{m,j} e_j$ $e_{i,hex} = [h_{i,hex} - h_0 - T_0 (s_{i,hex} - s_0)]_{hex}$ $[h_{i,hex} - h_0 - T_0 (s_{i,hex} - s_0)]_{hex}$	<p>Symbols: U—heat transfer coefficient, A—heat transfer area Subscripts: <i>hex</i>—heat exchanger</p>
Packed-bed storage	<p>Lögristic cumulative temperature distribution function [72]: $T(x) = T_{min} + \frac{T_{max} - T_{min}}{1 + e^{-\frac{x-\mu}{\sigma}}}$ One-dimensional heat transfer equations [37]: $\rho_s C_{ps} \frac{\partial T_s}{\partial t} = s \frac{\partial^2 T_s}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\alpha h_{eff}}{1-\varepsilon} (T_f - T_s),$ $\rho_f \frac{\partial (C_p T_f)}{\partial t} + \rho_f \mu_x \frac{\partial (C_p T_f)}{\partial x} = \frac{\alpha h_{eff}}{\varepsilon} (T_s - T_f),$</p>	<p>Charging exergy efficiency $\eta_{ex,cha} = \frac{q_{m,air} \cdot \Delta e_{i,air} + q_{m,h,cha} \cdot \Delta e_{h,cha}}{W_{cha} \cdot t_{cha} + q_{m,c,cha} \cdot \Delta e_{c,cha}}$ [45, 68] Discharging exergy efficiency $\eta_{ex,dis} = \frac{W_{dis} \cdot t_{dis} + q_{m,dis} \cdot \Delta e_{c,dis}}{q_{m,air} \cdot \Delta e_{i,air} + q_{m,h,dis} \cdot \Delta e_{h,dis}}$ [45, 68] $\eta_{ex,eqv} = \frac{W_{dis,net} \cdot t_{dis} + q_{m,c,dis} \cdot \Delta e_{c,dis} + q_{m,h,cha} \cdot \Delta e_{h,cha}}{W_{cha,net} \cdot t_{cha}}$ [122]</p>	<p>Symbols: ρ—density, μ/W—time evolution parameter, ε—void fraction, λ—heat conductivity, α—heat exchange surface per volume, u—axial velocity, h_{eff}—the volumetric heat transfer coefficient Subscripts: <i>min</i>—minimum, <i>max</i>—maximum, <i>s</i>—solid material, <i>f</i>—fluid,</p>
Round trip efficiency	$RTE = \frac{W_{cha} \cdot t_{cha}}{W_{dis} \cdot t_{dis}}$	<p>Equivalent round trip efficiency (tri-generation system) $RTE_{eqv} = \frac{W_{dis,net} \cdot t_{dis} + \frac{\dot{Q}_h}{COF_h} + \frac{\dot{Q}_c}{COF_c}}{W_{cha,net} \cdot t_{cha}}$ [121]</p>	<p>Symbols: t—duration/h. Subscripts: <i>cha</i>—charge, <i>dis</i>—discharge, <i>Lair</i>—liquid air, <i>hot</i>—hot fluid, <i>cold</i>—cold fluid, <i>ex</i>—exergy</p>
Equivalent round trip efficiency (tri-generation system)	$RTE_{eqv} = \frac{W_{dis,net} \cdot t_{dis} + \frac{\dot{Q}_h}{COF_h} + \frac{\dot{Q}_c}{COF_c}}{W_{cha,net} \cdot t_{cha}}$ [121]	Δe —exergy difference Subscripts: <i>heat/h</i> —heat energy, <i>cold/c</i> —cold energy, <i>net</i> —net power	

state), an RTE of $\sim 42.8\%$, and a combined heat and power energy efficiency of $\sim 82.1\%$. Tafone *et al* [112] investigated, both numerically and experimentally, the effects of a cold packed-bed store packed with a PCM on LAES performance. Their techno-economic analyses showed a reduction of specific energy consumption by 15.2% compared to a system with sensible thermal energy storage, the payback period is around three years. There are very few studies on the development of dynamic models for LAES. Guo *et al* [113] developed a dynamic model for LAES, which considered the volume effect and thermal inertia to understand the transient performance and control methods. Their results indicated a 10% of load step-down method and a combination control model would be suitable to achieve a shorter load balance time and a lower dynamic overshoot. Cui *et al* [114] developed a modular dynamic simulation model for LAES discharge unit, which considered the characteristics of key components and dynamic changes of thermodynamic parameters, and provided information on control strategy design, and the effects of rotor speed rising rate and frequency disturbance. Their subsequent work [115] reported a dynamic model for a 12.5 MW LAES system, showing the effects of different operating conditions of the LAES discharging unit, which are useful for the development of schemes for start-up and primary frequency regulation. Their work, however, did not include the dynamics of the whole LAES system. Lu *et al* [116] studied the impact of the rotor time constant and valve closing time on the rotor speed and shutdown time of a LAES discharging unit. They concluded that the rotor time constant should be less than 7 s, and the closing time of the control valve should not exceed 1.5 s, to meet the safety requirements.

As LAES and CAES share some similar processes and equipment as mentioned earlier, knowledge of dynamic modelling of CAES could be adopted for the dynamic studies of LAES. They are therefore briefly summarised in the following. Luo *et al* [123] developed a multi-physical model for an integrated electrical power system with A-CAES, including mathematical descriptions of key components. Their simulation results indicated that their toolkit developed could be used for dynamic modelling, real performance analysis and control strategy implementation. Mazloum *et al* [124] modelled the dynamic behaviour of an isobaric CAES system by using Dymola, where the mechanical inertia of turbines and the thermal inertia of HEXs and storage tanks were taken into account. Their model was shown to be capable of evaluating the system response time, and hence providing the primary and secondary reserve. Li *et al* [125] developed a dynamic model for an A-CAES system integrated with a micro-grid to investigate the capability to serve as back-up power for the community. They also performed an economic analysis to show the benefits under different micro-grid configurations, power supply reliabilities and diesel prices. Their results indicated that the A-CAES system could restore power supply within several minutes and achieve profitability under certain conditions. He *et al* [126] developed a detailed component and system model for an A-CAES system integrated with a packed-bed thermal store filled with different materials including rock and PCM. Their component models were validated by experimental data, and their dynamic simulation results indicated that the PCM-filled heat store could have a reduced volume by 43.5% and a higher cycle efficiency compared with rock-filled heat store.

3.4. Economic modelling

A number of studies have been reported on the economic analyses of LAES. These studies used different methods, which can be divided broadly into two categories summarised in the following.

- *Components cost estimation model* Nabat *et al* [127] and Wu *et al* [128] conducted economic analyses by considering the purchasing cost of each component to obtain the total capital expenditure (CAPEX). Hamdy *et al* [44, 68] used past purchase orders and cost estimating charts to obtain cost models of individual components with the bare module cost factor considered in the estimation. Georgiou *et al* [129] adopted several costing models for components based on chemical engineering cost estimation methods, taking into account some uncertainties. These approaches could be regarded as cost estimation method for components and table 3 provides a summary, which are based on machine power scale, heat transfer area, pressure ratio, mass flow rate and efficiency etc.
- *Subsystem cost estimation model* Vecchi *et al* [130], Xie *et al* [131] and Sveinbjörnsson *et al* [132] estimated the capital costs of LAES plants based on the cost estimation for the pilot plant data and the so-called 'six-rule' capacity scaling methods. In such a method, the capital investment is divided into three major subsystems of charging, discharging and storage, as described by equations (1)–(4) with P being rated power output/consumption, CAPEX the capital expenditure, E the energy stored, and subscripts *cha*-for charge process, *dis*-for discharge process, *sto*-for storage process, and *tot*-for total. The method can therefore be called subsystem estimation method. The units of charging and discharging powers are in MW, the storage capacity is in MWh, and base costs are based on 2012 value in 1000 US\$. These equations are found to have an agreement within 6%.

Table 3. Individual key component cost models.

Components	Types	Cost model	Currency	Parameters introduction	References
Compressor	Reciprocating	$k_r \beta_c \dot{V}$ with $\dot{V} = \omega V_{sp}$	£ 2016	k_r —the cost factor, a typical value 8000 £ (m ³ s ⁻¹) ⁻¹ , ω —rotational speed (r s ⁻¹), V_{sp} —the swept volume (m ³), β_c —the pressure ratio, \dot{V} —the volume flow (m ³ s ⁻¹)	[133]
Expander	Turbomachine General	$39.5 \dot{m}_f \cdot \frac{\beta_c \cdot \log \beta_c}{0.9 - \eta_{is}}$ $7900 \cdot X^{0.62}$	\$ 2017 \$ 2009	\dot{m}_f —mass flow rate (kg s ⁻¹), η_{is} —the isentropic efficiency X —compressor capacity (kW)	[134] [135]
	Turbo-machine	$479.34 \dot{m}_f \cdot \log(\beta_c) \frac{(1 + e^{0.056 \dot{m}_f - 54.4})}{(0.93 - \eta_{is})}$	\$ 2013	\dot{m}_f —mass flow rate (kg s ⁻¹), η_{is} —the isentropic efficiency, β_c —the expansion ratio, T_{in} —inlet temperature of turbine (K)	[136]
Heat exchanger	Cryo-turbine General	$5010 \cdot \left(\frac{X}{10}\right)^{0.67}$ $1100 \cdot (X)^{0.81}$	k€ 2017 \$ 2009	X —turbine power (MW)	[68] [137]
	Evaporator	$16000 \cdot \left(\frac{X}{100}\right)^{0.6}$	\$ 2020	X —heat transfer area (m ²)	[127]
	Intercooler	$12000 \cdot \left(\frac{X}{100}\right)^{0.6}$	\$ 2020	X —heat transfer area (m ²)	[127]
	Multi-stream HEX	$32800 \cdot \left(\frac{X}{80}\right)^{0.68}$	\$ 2005	X —heat transfer area (m ²)	[127]
	General	$\log_{10}(C_{hex0}) = 4.325 - 0.303 \cdot \log_{10}(X)$ $+ 0.1634 \cdot \log_{10}(X)^2$ $C_{hex} = C_{hex0} \cdot P_f$	\$ 2009	X —heat transfer area (m ²), P_f —pressure factor, C_{hex0} —base cost of heat exchanger	[135]
Packed-bed storage	Detailed	$c_m V_p + c_f V_i + c_{pv} V_{pv} (P_0 + \Delta P + \rho_m g L)$ $c_m = 500 \text{ £ m}^{-3}, c_f = 1400 \text{ £ m}^{-3}$, $c_{pv} = 200 \text{ £ (m}^3 \text{ bar)}^{-1}$	£ 2016	$P_f = 1.63 + 1.66 \cdot 10 \wedge 0.0388 - 0.1127 \cdot \log_{10}(P) + 0.08173 \cdot \log_{10}(P)^2$ V —material volume, c —material cost per unit volume, m, i, pv —packed material, insulation and pressure vessel, P_0 —ambient pressure (bar), ΔP —pressure drop across walls (bar), ρ_m —density of packed material (kg m ⁻³), L —the height of store (m)	[138]
Tank	General	$13.75 \cdot X$	k€ 2017	X —cold storage capacity (MWh)	[68]
	For thermal oil	$423 \cdot X$	\$ 2018	X —tank volume (m ³)	[23]
	For methanol	$572 \cdot X$	\$ 2018	X —tank volume (m ³)	[32]
	For propane	$1326 \cdot X$	\$ 2018	X —tank volume (m ³)	[6]
Pump	For liquid air	$0.256 \cdot \left(\frac{X}{100}\right)^{0.9}$	£ 2012	X —tank weight (tons)	[68]
	Pressurized tank	$4500 \cdot X^{0.6} + 10000$	\$ 2009	X —tank weight (tons)	[135]
	Cryo-pump	$483 \cdot X$	\$ 2018	X —pump power capacity (kW)	[128]
Heat transfer media	General pump	$1120 \cdot X^{0.8}$	\$ 2012	X —power (kW)	[136]
	Thermal oil	$5000 \cdot X$	\$ 2018	X —mass of thermal oil (kg)	[128]
	Methanol	$519 \cdot X$	\$ 2018	X —mass of methanol (kg)	[128]
Air-liquid air separator Motor-generator	Propane	$264 \cdot X$	\$ 2018	X —volume of propane (m ³)	[128]
	—	$114.5 \cdot X^{0.67}$ $60 \cdot X^{0.95}$	\$ 2019 \$ 2009	X —mas flow rate (kg s ⁻¹) X —power (kW)	[127] [139]

$$\text{CAPEX}_{\text{dis}} = 5653 \left(\frac{P_{\text{dis}}}{10} \right)^{0.6} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{CAPEX}_{\text{cha}} = 11406 \left(\frac{P_{\text{cha}}}{4} \right)^{0.6} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{CAPEX}_{\text{sto}} = 1778 \left(\frac{E_{\text{sto}}}{86} \right)^{0.6} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{CAPEX}_{\text{tot}} = \text{CAPEX}_{\text{dis}} + \text{CAPEX}_{\text{cha}} + \text{CAPEX}_{\text{sto}}. \quad (4)$$

Apart from the cost models discussed above, different economic indicators have also been investigated for LAES and its hybrid systems, to understand the economic competitiveness and advantages of LAES. These economic indicators and associated results are listed in table 4. With different power generation capacities, the specific power based capital cost is found to be between 850 and 2100 £ kW⁻¹, the specific energy based capital cost is in the range of 260–500 £ MWh⁻¹, the total LCOS varies between 105 and 345 \$ MWh⁻¹, the total LCOE varies from 81 to 236 £ MWh⁻¹ and the payback period is between 4 and 20 years. These economic parameters are also summarized in figure 6. One can see there are large ranges for these economic indicators, which is due to many factors, including installed capacity, equipment operation parameters, models for equipment cost, quoted price from suppliers, power/energy cost, electricity/cooling/heating price and economic assumptions, system operation modes and hybrid modes etc. Though the techno-economic analysis is an important basis for evaluating the LAES technology, it is difficult if not impossible at this stage to obtain accurate economic estimates without more data particularly actual operation data. The ranges of these parameters can only be used as references.

Other parameters related to economic analysis of LAES include the OMCs, inflation rate, cooling and heating energy prices, electricity prices and annual operating cycles and days etc. Table 5 summaries the data from the literature.

4. Techno-economic analysis

4.1. Standalone LAES systems

4.1.1. LAES system without excess compression heat utilization

LAES was first proposed and studied without utilizing the excess compression heat. Most studies on such systems were on the analyses of system energy and exergy efficiencies and some on economic analyses.

- *Energy analyses* Guizzi *et al* [35] and Xue *et al* [145] found that a 50% of RTE could be reached for a stand-alone LAES. Sciacovelli *et al* [37] investigated a 100 MW/300 MWh stand-alone LAES system with packed-bed based cold store. An RTE of around 50% can be reached, but the power consumption during the charging process increased by 25% due to the formation of thermocline in the packed bed. Liang *et al* [47] and Liu *et al* [146] developed an optimization scheme and an algorithm to optimize the operational parameters, including the charging/discharging pressures, temperatures, and system configurations. They found an optimal efficiency as high as 60%–63%.
- *Exergy analysis* Ameal *et al* [147] studied the exergy destruction and recovery within an LAES cycle, and concluded that cold and heat recovery was of high importance. Guizzi *et al* [35] found that the major exergy loss came from the compression and expansion processes. Vecchi *et al* [72] analysed the exergy distribution of LAES at both component and system levels with the system operated under the design and off-design conditions. Hamdy *et al* [137] conducted an overall exergy analysis of LAES by using a ‘fuel/product’ method and found the irreversibility of the liquefaction process accounted for as high as 75%. Incer-Valverde *et al* [148] split the irreversibility of LAES cycle into avoidable and unavoidable parts, and concluded that the major potential improvement would lie in the main HEX of the PRU, which could avoid 60% of exergy destruction.
- *Economic analyses* Xie *et al* [131] assessed the economics of a decoupled LAES system when participating in the UK electricity service markets. The results indicated that a large-scale LAES with high-grade waste heat (150 °C) would be profitable. Lin *et al* [142] found similar results for an LAES system (~200 MW), which was shown to achieve a payback period of 25.7–39.4 years without introducing external waste heat. Wang *et al* [109] found that the payback period of standalone LAES systems ranged between 9.6 and 31.7 years when the capacity increased from 10 MWh d⁻¹ to 200 MWh d⁻¹ at a peak-valley electricity price ratio of 3.3:1. Clearly, maximising the utilization rate of the compression heat and/or the introduction of external waste heat to the stand-alone LAES system would shorten the payback period and hence improve the economic benefits.

Table 4. The economic metrics used in LAES studies.

Economic indexes	Formula and definition	Application cases
Levelized cost of energy (LCOE)	$LCOE = \frac{C_{inv, other} + C_{inv, LAES} + (\sum_{t=1}^N C_{OM, ann} \cdot (1+\sigma)^{-t})}{\sum_{t=1}^N W_d T_d (1+\sigma)^{-t}}$ <p>It represents the cost for producing 1 kWh of electricity for the combined power system.</p> <p>C_{inv}—capital investment, Amf—annual amortization factor, C_{OM} operation and maintenance cost, W_d—rated discharge power, T_d—rated discharge hours per year, ann—annual cost, $other$—other power systems</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) The LCOE of a multi-generation is 790 RNB MWh⁻¹ (2021) in Beijing [117]. (b) The LCOE of a LAES hybrid plant (60 MWe) is 179–186 \$ MWh⁻¹ [128]. (c) The LCOE of a LAES renewable hybrid plant is 81.89 ~130 € MWh⁻¹ (2022) [140]. (d) The LCOE of a 300 MW LAES: 161–171 € kWh⁻¹ [68].
Levelized cost of storage (LCOS)	$LCOS = \frac{C_{inv, LAES} + (\sum_{t=1}^N (C_{OM, ann} + C_{dec, ann}) \cdot (1+\sigma)^{-t})}{\sum_{t=1}^N W_d T_d (1+\sigma)^{-t}}$ <p>It represents the cost for producing 1 kWh of electricity for the storage system.</p> <p>C_{dec}—electricity cost, N—operating years, σ—discount rate, t—the year</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) LAES with an ORC: ~185.48 \$ MWh⁻¹ (2022) [141]. (b) LAES (12 MW/50 MWh): 140 ~ 460 \$ MWh⁻¹ [129].
Static Payback period (SPBP)	$SPBP = \frac{C_{inv, LAES} \cdot Amf + C_{OM, ann}}{C_{sav, ann}}$ <p>It represents the time period needed to recover the total investment.</p> <p>$C_{sav, ann}$—annual saving cost</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) SPBP of multi-functional LAES is ~7.04 years [117]. (b) SPBP of a LAES hybrid plant (200 MW) is 8.7–9.8 years [142]. (c) SPBP (arbitrage/STOR function) is ~20–35 years, but SPBP (arbitrage/FR function) is ~10–20 years [130].
Dynamic Payback period (DPBP)	$DPBP = \sum_{t=1}^N \frac{(C_{OM, ann} \cdot (1+\sigma)^{-t}) + C_{inv, LAES}}{\sum_{t=1}^N C_{sav, ann} (1+\sigma)^{-t}}$ <p>It represents the time period needed to recover the total investment considering the time value of money.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) DPBP of multi-functional LAES is ~6.09 years [117]. (b) DPBP of tri-generation LAES is ~5.46 years [122].
Net present value (NPV)—life cycle net savings of a project	$NPV = \sum_{t=1}^N \frac{(p_{rd} W_d T_d - p_c W_d T_c - C_{OM, ann} - C_{fuel, ann}) \cdot (1+\varepsilon)^t}{(1+\sigma)^t} - C_{inv, LAES}$ <p>It represents the total cash inflow and cash outflow.</p> <p>p_{rd}—price of discharging electricity, p_c—price of charging electricity, ε—escalation rate, C_{fuel}—fuel cost.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) The NPV of a tri-generation LAES over 30 years is 5483.8 k\$ [122]. (b) The NPV of a multi-functional LAES over 30 years is 5.19 million \$ [109].
Rate of return on investment (ROI)	$ROI = \frac{C_{sav, ann}}{C_{inv, LAES} \cdot Amf + C_{OM, ann}}$ <p>It represents the ratio of annual benefit to its annual investment</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) The ROI of a multi-functional LAES is 20.5% [117]. (b) The ROI of LAES at micro-grid scale (3 MW) is 20%–45% when providing arbitrage, wind firming and operating reserve [47].
Saving investment ratio (SIR)—the profitability of a project	$SIR = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (C_{bene, ann} (1+\sigma)^t)}{C_{inv, LAES}}$ <p>$C_{bene, ann}$—annual benefits</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) The base LAES with SIR at 1.24 [109]. (b) SIR of a multi-functional LAES with at 3.12 [109]. (c) SIR of a LAES with ORC is 3.1 [38].

(Continued.)

Table 4. (Continued.)

Economic indexes	Formula and definition	Application cases
Internal rate of return (IRR)	See NPV formula It represents the discount rate when the NPV of a project is equal to 0.	The IRR of a multi-functional LAES is 27% [117].
Specific power cost (SPC)	$C_P = \frac{C_{inv, LAES}}{W_d}$ W_d —the rated discharge power	(a) CES with Claude, Heylandt and Kapitza cycles are at 700 ~ 900 € kW ⁻¹ [44]. (b) CES with different integrations has specific cost at 1100 ~ 2000 € kW ⁻¹ [68]. (c) LAES (12 MW/50 MWh): 1430 ~ 2730 \$ kW ⁻¹ [129].
Specific energy cost (SEC)	$C_E = \frac{C_{inv, LAES}}{E_{store}}$ E_{store} —the stored energy, kWh	LAES (12 MW/50 MWh): 350 ~ 670 \$ MWh ⁻¹ [129].
Specific benefits (SB): benefits per sold energy	$SB = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^{8760} W_d P_d - (C_{inv, other} Amf + C_{inv, LAES} Amf + C_{OM, am})}{\sum_{t=1}^{8760} W_d \cdot 1 h}$	The SB of an LAES renewable hybrid plant is 5.4 ~ 17 € MWh ⁻¹ (2022) [140].
CO ₂ avoided cost (CAC)	$CAC = \frac{LCOF_{capture} - LCOF_{ref}}{e_{CO_2, ref} - e_{CO_2, capture}}$ ref —reference case, $capture$ —CO ₂ capture case, e —specific CO ₂ emission	20 € ton ⁻¹ CO ₂ [143].

Notes: Amf—annual amortized factor, $Amf = \frac{IR(1+IR)^N}{(1+IR)^N - 1}$, IR—interest rate.

Figure 6. The economic indicators of stand-alone and hybrid LAES systems.

Table 5. Other economic parameters of LAES plant.

Economic parameters	Value
Operation and maintenance costs (OMC)	1.5% [44] to 6% [144] of the fixed capital investment (FCI)
Inflation rate	2% [122] ~ 5% [44]
Discount rate	7% [131] ~ 10% [140]
Installation cost	25% of FCI [128]
Instrumentation and controls	8% of FCI [128]
Cooling energy price	13.5 [122] ~ 35 £ MWh ⁻¹ [117]
Heating energy price	28 ~ 40 £ MWh ⁻¹ [117]
Peak electricity price	80 [72] ~ 137 £ MWh ⁻¹ [144]
Valley electricity price	20 [72] ~ 30 £ MWh ⁻¹ [144]
STOR availability fee, utilization fee	4.25 £ MW h ⁻¹ , 150 £ MWh ⁻¹ [44]
Fast reserve availability fee, utilization fee, positional fee	210 £ h ⁻¹ , 100 £ MWh ⁻¹ , 90 £ h ⁻¹ [44]
Charge/discharge full cycles	300 [72] ~ 365 [128] cycles/year
Plant lifetime/years	25 [143] ~ 30 [122]

4.1.2. LAES system with excess compression heat utilization

Around 20%–40% of compression heat (recovered from the LAES charging process) is not effectively used in many analyses, which provides an opportunity to improve the system RTE [35, 38, 149]. As a result, different solutions have been proposed to use the excess compression heat and associated techno-economic analyses have been carried out. These studies include power and cooling generation technologies at medium-to-low temperature, such as ORC, ABC, KC, and TEG, and district heating network, as illustrated in figure 7.

The ORC is the most widely studied method for excess compression heat recovery and utilisation in LAES plants. She *et al* [38] performed a thermo-economic analysis on an integrated LAES-ORC system. They found, compared to the stand-alone configuration, the integrated system could increase the exergy efficiency and RTE by 9%–12%, with a payback period of as low as three years when introducing a vapour refrigeration cycle as a heat sink for the ORC. Peng *et al* [45] proposed a similar configuration to replace vapour compression chiller with a waste-heat powered water-ammonia ABC. Their technical analysis showed that the LAES-ORC system without the ABC (using ambient water as heat sink directly) had a simpler configuration but a higher RTE than the system with ABC, and both of them could have an RTE over 60%. Tafone *et al* [150] compared the economics of standalone LAES, LAES-ORC and Li-ion batteries. Their results showed that the LCOS of the stand-alone LAES was decreased by 10% when LAES-ORC system operated in a poly-generation mode.

The KC cycle can be used for recovering the excess compression heat efficiently. Ebrahimi *et al* [151] proposed an LAES-KC cogeneration system, where PCM was used to recover and store the LAES excess compression heat. By reducing the charging pressure and increasing the discharging pressure of the LAES, the RTE and the electrical storage efficiency of this hybrid system were shown to be enhanced to 47.6% and 61.6%, respectively. Zhang *et al* [43] proposed an ammonia-water based KC cycle coupled with LAES for excess compression heat recovery. An increase in the RTE by $\sim 10\%$ was obtained compared with the stand-alone LAES without KC. The same researchers [152] compared the performance of KC and ORC based cycles for LAES excess compression heat recovery and utilization. Their results showed that ORCs generally could outperform KCs with optimal working fluids and conditions. The subcritical ORCs with dry fluids were found to be more suitable for excess compression heat recovery. KCs, on the other hand, would require a higher operating pressure, which would require a more complex system design and a higher investment.

Apart from the use of ORC or KC individually for power generation, Nabat *et al* [127, 153] studied a combined ORC and KC system with TEG for power generation. For the ORC-TEG hybridization [127], both electrical power and hot water could be produced through a cascaded arrangement of ORC and TEG, to fully utilize the excess heat, leading to an improved system RTE and exergy efficiency to 61.1% and 52.8%, respectively, 6.59% and 3.28% higher than systems without the excess heat utilization. A payback period of 3.91 years was shown, together with a final profit of \$18.6 million. With a KC-TEG hybridization [153], the RTE was shown to be increased to 61.6%, with a payback period of 3.5 years and a total profit of \$26.3 million for a 30 year operation if an optimal charging pressure of 150.9 bar and a discharging pressure of 84.4 bar were used. The combined LAES-TEG system was investigated by Liu *et al* [154] as well, their techno-economic analysis suggested an optimal hot water outlet temperature of $60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ – $80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, an overall efficiency increase of 1.7%, and a payback period as low as three years.

Tafone *et al* [51, 150] studied a LAES-based poly-generation system, with LAES integrated with an ORC and a waste heat-driven ABC to provide electricity, heat and cold energy for district heating and cooling networks. Their results showed that the overall RTE of the LAES for the tri-generation could reach 45%–56%. She *et al* [121] proposed a hybrid LAES system to provide cooling, heating, hot water and power simultaneously. Their equivalent RTE was shown to be between 52%–76%, with the highest achieved at a charging pressure of 5 MPa. Cui *et al* [117] studied a novel multifunctional LAES system for the provision of

heating, cooling, electricity and fresh air. Such a LAES system was shown to reach an energy efficiency of 75.4% with an LCOE of 0.79 CNY kWh⁻¹ in Beijing. Al-Zareer *et al* [155] proposed an LAES system for district heating and cooling applications, with a gas turbine and an ORC for power generation during discharging, and a solid-gas reactor for heating and cooling. They showed that overall energy and exergy efficiencies of 72.1% and 53.7%, respectively, could be achieved. Vecchi *et al* [156] performed a techno-economic analysis on an LAES-based system for heating, cooling and power applications, and showed that the RTE of the overall system increased by 54.8%, and the operational cost was reduced by 8%–12%. A summary of the waste heat utilization approaches is provided in table 6.

4.2. Integrated LAES systems

4.2.1. LAES integration with an external cold source

A LAES system requires cold energy to liquefy air during charging, but the recovered cold energy during discharging is insufficient with ~18% of shortage [36]. The use of an external high-grade cold source can therefore improve the system RTE. An example of such external cold energy source is from the regasification of liquefied natural gas (LNG). This is discussed in the following.

The integration of LNG regasification with a LAES system is illustrated in figure 8. Table 7 provides a summary of relevant studies. One can see that the LAES-LNG integration can be divided into three sub-categories of direct utilization, indirect utilization through cold storage, and hybrid utilization:

- *Direct utilization* The LNG regasification occurs in the cold box of LAES, releasing high-grade cold energy to cool down and liquefy the air. This sub-category has a lack of flexibility, as it requires LNG regasification and air liquefaction to operate simultaneously. Besides, the waste cold energy released from the LNG depends on the NG demands, which is often fluctuating, thus adding operation difficulties of such an LAES-LNG integrated system [157].
- *Indirect utilization* This sub-category uses a CES system to capture and store the cold energy released from the LNG regasification. During LAES charging, the stored cold energy from the LNG regasification is reused for air liquefaction, increasing the flexibility of the integrated system.
- *Hybrid utilization* This is a hybrid of the direct and indirect utilization sub-categories. The cold energy from the LNG is recovered either in the cold box/HEXs of the LAES directly or through the CES unit, depending on the time of day (peak time and off-peak time [158]).

The working modes of the three sub-categories of LNG cold energy utilisation and their energy and exergy efficiencies are listed in table 7. Additionally, the LNG cold energy can also be used as a heat sink for the integrated LAES-ORC or LAES-Brayton cycles to enhance the total output power and overall efficiency [159, 160].

4.2.2. LAES integration with external heat sources

Although compression heat may not be effectively used in some cases, the use of external heat sources can be of an advantage from either or both economical and system efficiency aspects, the work summary was shown as in table 8. Briola *et al* [172] proposed a LAES system with a gas turbine cycle. Their energy analysis revealed a specific work of the charging circuit at 486 kJ kg⁻¹, and a storage efficiency (a new indicator) of 2.173. Their economic analysis indicated a differential Net Present Value Ratio of 2.764 under an optimistic scenario. Hanak *et al* [143] proposed the combination of cryogenic oxygen storage with an oxy-coal fired power plant to enhance overall efficiency and economics. Their results showed enhanced flexibility by the combined system, as well as daily financial return by 3.8%–4.1%. Colbertaldo *et al* [173] proposed and analysed the use of stored liquid air to a gas turbine combustor, and found that the generated power could be doubled compared with the system with air compressors, and the RTE could reach 70%. Krawczyk *et al* [174] studied a LAES system (270 MW, 1080 MWh) with a combustion chamber. Under a charging pressure of 12 MPa, a discharging pressure of 2.1 MPa, and an expansion turbine inlet temperature of 1300 °C, the system RTE was found to be 55.2%. Barsali *et al* [175] modelled a hybrid system with liquid air as an energy storage medium and LNG as a fuel, an equivalent RTE ranging from 82% with carbon capture at 100 bar to 104% without carbon capture at 150 bar can be obtained. Kim *et al* [170] investigated a combined renewable-LAES-LNG system, in which renewables are to provide electricity for charging LAES, and LNG regasification and combustion to help increase power generation during LAES discharging. The energy and exergy efficiencies of the combined system were shown to be 64.2% and 62.1%, respectively, and the system LCOE ranging from 142 to 190 \$ MWh⁻¹ depending on the system size and storage time.

Due to carbon emission of NG and coal combustion, the use of external heat from non-carbon sources to the LAES system has been studied. For example, Li *et al* [87] proposed the use of heat from a nuclear power plant for load-shifting and peak-shaving of nuclear power plants and power output enhancement of LAES.

Table 6. Summary of the recovery of LAES excess compression heat.

Authors/Ref.	The systems for compression heat utilization	Working fluids	Round trip efficiency (η_{RTE})	Exergy efficiency (η_{ex})	Economic indicators and values
She <i>et al</i> [38]	LAES-ORC Heat source: compression heat Heat sink: vapour compression refrigeration cycle (VCRC)	Liquid air for LAES R32/ R502/ R134a for ORC R134a for VCRC	Up to 62%	Charging: 83%–87% Discharging: 80%–82%	PBP for the proposed ORC: ~3 years (based on 5 MW/40 MWh LAES)
Peng <i>et al</i> [45]	LAES-ORC Heat source: compression heat Heat sink: ABC or ambient water	Liquid air for LAES R134a for ORC Ammonia-water for ABC	Up to 64%	Charging: 85%	/
Tafone <i>et al</i> [51, 150]	LAES-ORC—(ABC) Heat source: compression heat Heat sink: ambient	Liquid nitrogen for LAES R134a/R245fa for ORC water-LiBr for ABC	48%–53% for electricity 45%–56% for trigeneration ^a	/	LCOS: 0.16 € kWh ⁻¹ (100 MW/400 MWh, 365 cycles per year)
She <i>et al</i> [121]	LAES-ABC-direct heating Heat source: compression heat	Liquid air for LAES LiBr-water for ABC	52%–76% for trigeneration ^a	Charging: 87% Discharging: 84%	Primary energy savings: 12.1 MWh Avoided carbon dioxide emissions: 2.3 ton (1 MW/8 MWh) SPBP: ~5 years LCOE: 0.79 CNY kWh ⁻¹ (1.5 MW/12 MWh)
Cui <i>et al</i> [117]	LAES-ABC-direct heating Heat source: compression heat	Liquid air for LAES	75.4% for trigeneration ^b	/	SPBP: ~5 years LCOE: 0.79 CNY kWh ⁻¹ (1.5 MW/12 MWh)
Al-Zareer <i>et al</i> [155]	LAES-ORC-solid gas reactor Heat source: compression heat/combustion heat Heat sink: ambient	Liquid air for LAES Ammonia for solid gas reactor	72.1% for cooling supply (0 °C) ^b	53.7%	/
Vecchi <i>et al</i> [156]	LAES-direct cooling-direct heating	Liquid air for LAES	72.8% for rigeneration ^b	/	Cost saving metric: 8%–13%
Ebrahimi <i>et al</i> [151]	LAES-KC (KC-based cogeneration unit) Heat source: compression heat	Liquid air for LAES Ammonia-water for KC	47.6% for cogeneration ^b	~40%	/
Zhang <i>et al</i> [152]	LAES-ORC Heat source: compression heat	Liquid air for LAES n-Pentane for subcritical ORC R152a for supercritical ORC	~57%	~58%–61%	/
Nabat <i>et al</i> [127]	LAES-ORC-TEG Heat source: compression heat and high-temperature electric heater Heat sink: ambient water	Liquid air for LAES R717 for ORC	~61% for cogeneration ^b	~53%	SPBP: ~4 years (9.6 MW/38.4 MWh)

(Continued.)

Table 6. (Continued.)

Authors/Ref.	The systems for compression heat utilization	Working fluids	Round trip efficiency (η_{RTE})	Exergy efficiency (η_{ex})	Economic indicators and values
Nabat et al [153]	LAES-KC-TEG Heat source: compression heat and high-temperature electric heater Heat sink: ambient water	Liquid air for LAES Ammonia-water for KC	~62%	Charging: 76.4% Discharging: 90.32%	SPBP: ~4 years (~7 MW/14 MWh)

$$^a \eta_{RTE} = \frac{W_{dis} + \frac{Q_{cooling}}{COP_c} + \frac{Q_{heating}}{COP_h}}{W_{ch}}$$

$$^b \eta_{RTE} = \frac{W_{dis} + Q_{cooling} + Q_{heating}}{W_{ch}}$$

They showed that the RTE of LAES could reach ~70% and the peak power of the integrated system can be 2.7 times that of the rated nuclear power plant. Cetin et al [176] developed a system combining LAES with a geothermal power plant, with the geothermal water serving as an external heat source at ~180 °C for the expansion process of LAES. Their analyses indicated a LAES RTE of 46.7%, and an overall system efficiency of ~24.4%.

4.2.3. LAES integration with renewables

Recent years have seen a number of studies on the direct integration of LAES with renewable generation to deal with intermittency and time-shifting of renewables, including solar thermal heat, solar PV, wind, and geothermal energy. These studies are summarised in table 9 and explained as the followings:

- *Integration with solar thermal* Solar thermal system can provide medium and high-temperature heat. Such heat can be used to increase air inlet temperature of turbine during LAES discharging process. Li et al [177]

Table 7. Summary of the integration methods between the LNG regasification process and the LAES.

Focus/Ref.	LNG regasification working mode	LAES working mode	Liquid air storage pressure	Round trip efficiency (η_{RTE}) (definition and result)	Exergy efficiency (η_{ex}) ^c
Option I—direct utilization [161]	Off-peak: LNG for direct refrigeration in cold box Peak + flat: no description	Off-peak: air liquefaction (charging) with LNG and CES ^a as cold source Peak: power recovery (discharging) with TES ^b and external heat for air heating + CES	0.2 MPa	70.5% $(\eta_{\text{RTE}} = \frac{W_{\text{dis}}}{W_{\text{ch}}})$	50.73%
Option I—direct utilization [162]	Off-peak: LNG for direct refrigeration in cold box and for power generation Peak + flat: no description	Off-peak: air liquefaction (charging) with LNG and CES as cold source Peak: power recovery (discharging) with TES for air heating + CES	0.1–0.2 MPa	60.1% $(\eta_{\text{RTE}} = \frac{W_{\text{dis}}}{W_{\text{ch}} - W_{\text{LNG,off}}})$	/
Option I—direct utilization [163, 164]	Off-peak: LNG for direct refrigeration in cold box Peak + flat: LNG for direct power generation without being integrated with LAES	Off-peak: air liquefaction (charging) with LNG as cold source Peak: power recovery (discharging) with external heat for air heating	~2.5 MPa	95.2% $(\eta_{\text{RTE}} = \frac{W_{\text{dis}} + W_{\text{LNG,peak}} - W_{\text{LNG,flat}}}{W_{\text{ch}}})$	/
Option I—direct utilization [165]	Off-peak: LNG for direct refrigeration in LAES inter-stage coolers and cold box and for power generation Peak: LNG for direct power generation without being integrated with LAES	Off-peak: air liquefaction (charging) with LNG as cold source Peak: power recovery (discharging) at ambient temperature + CES	0.15 MPa	129.2% $(\eta_{\text{RTE}} = \frac{W_{\text{dis}}}{W_{\text{ch}}})$	35% ^d
Option I—direct utilization [157, 166, 167]	Off-peak: LNG for direct refrigeration in LAES inter-stage coolers + LNG expansion shaft work for compression in LAES Peak: not working	Off-peak: air liquefaction (charging) with LNG as cold source and LNG expansion shaft work for compression Peak: power recovery (discharging) at ambient temperature	4.4–21 MPa [157, 166] 3.6–1.8 MPa [167]	105.64% [157], 122.82% [166] 135.98 [167] $(\eta_{\text{RTE}} = \frac{W_{\text{dis}} - W_{\text{LNG,off}}}{W_{\text{ch}}})$	38% ^d [157], 43% ^d [166]
Option I—direct utilization [168]	Off-peak: LNG for direct refrigeration in LAES inter-stage coolers + LNG expansion shaft work for compression in LAES Peak: not working	Off-peak: air liquefaction (charging) with LNG as cold source and LNG expansion shaft work for compression Peak: power recovery (discharging) with additional ORC at ambient temperature	4.4–21 MPa	141.88% $(\eta_{\text{RTE}} = \frac{W_{\text{dis}} - W_{\text{LNG,off}}}{W_{\text{ch}}})$	47% ^d
Option I—indirect utilization [169]	Off-peak: LNG with CES + direct expansion power generation Peak: LNG with CES + direct expansion power generation	Off-peak: air liquefaction (charging) with CES as cold source Peak: power recovery (discharging) with TES for air heating + CES	0.1 MPa	88% $(\eta_{\text{RTE}} = \frac{W_{\text{dis}} + W_{\text{LNG,peak}}}{W_{\text{ch}} - W_{\text{LNG,off}}})$	64%

(Continued.)

Table 7. (Continued.)

Focus/Ref.	LNG regasification working mode	LAES working mode	Liquid air storage pressure	Round trip efficiency (η_{RTE}) (definition and result)	Exergy efficiency (η_{ex}) ^c
Option I—indirect utilization [170]	Off-peak: not working Peak-time: LNG with CES + direct expansion power generation	Off-peak: air liquefaction (charging) with CES as cold source Peak: power recovery (discharging) with fuel combustion + CES	0.2 MPa	64.2%	62.1%
Option I—hybrid utilization [158]	Off-peak: LNG for direct refrigeration in LAES cold box Peak: LNG with CES	Off-peak: air liquefaction (charging) with LNG and CES as cold source Peak: power recovery (discharging) with external heat for air heating	3.7 MPa	85.1% $(\eta_{RTE} = \frac{W_{dis}}{W_{ch}})$	56.7% ^d
Option I—hybrid utilization [171]	Off-peak: LNG for direct refrigeration in LAES inter-stage coolers + direct expansion power generation Peak: LNG with CES + direct expansion power generation	Off-peak: air liquefaction (charging) with LNG and CES as cold source Peak: power recovery (discharging) at ambient temperature	3.7 MPa	187.4% $(\eta_{RTE} = \frac{W_{dis} + W_{LNG,peak}}{W_{ch} - W_{LNG,off}})$	57.8% ^d
Option II [159, 160]	Off-peak: LNG with CES + direct expansion power generation Peak: LNG with CES + direct expansion power generation	Off-peak: air liquefaction (charging) with CES as cold source Peak: power recovery (discharging) with TES for air heating + Brayton cycle driven by TES and CES + CES	0.1 MPa	72% $(\eta_{RTE} = \frac{W_{dis} + W_{Brayton}}{W_{ch}})$	57%

^a CES—cryogenic energy storage.

^b TES—heat energy storage (compression heat storage).

^c $\eta_{ex} = \frac{W_{dis}}{W_{in} + (E_{kin} - E_{kin})}$.

^d Recalculated by authors.

*Equations: Ex—external cold and heat sources exergy; LHV—low heating value; WLNG—Power generation by LNG; W—Power consumption or generation.

*Subscripts: ch—charging process; dis—discharging process; off—off peak time; peak—peak time; flat—flat time.

Table 8. Literature summary of LAES integrated with external heat source.

References	External heat source	System scale (MW h ⁻¹)	Turbine inlet temperature (K)	Turbine inlet pressure (MPa)	RTE (%)	Economic indicator
Li <i>et al</i> [87]	Waste heat from nuclear power plant	700/1 h	~280 °C	11.5	~70	\
Briola <i>et al</i> [172]	Liquid air burns with LNG	58.2	~1250 °C	2.4	~54.05	Net Present Value Ratio: 2.764
Cetin <i>et al</i> [176]	Geothermal heat source	100/3 h	~127 °C	18	~46.7	\
Hanak <i>et al</i> [143]	Oxy-combustion for coal-fired power plant	572/4 h	~1300 °C	\	~35 (Thermal efficiency)	LCOS: 54.7 € MWh ⁻¹ Specific power cost: 1900 € kW ⁻¹
Chino <i>et al</i> [173]	Liquid air burns with LNG	100/5 h	~345 °C	1.25	~70	\
Piotr <i>et al</i> [174]	Liquid air burns with LNG	270/4 h	~1300 °C	2.1	~55.2	\
Barsali <i>et al</i> [175]	Liquid air burns with LNG	\	~996 °C	15	~90	\
Kim <i>et al</i> [170]	Liquid air burns with LNG	33	~1400 °C	7	~64.2	LCOE: 142.5–190.0 \$ MWh ⁻¹ Power specific cost: 1284.7 \$ kW ⁻¹ Energy specific cost: 439.7 \$ MWh ⁻¹

Table 9. Literature summary of LAES integrated with renewables.

LAES integrated with Renewables	Integration method	System scale (MW h ⁻¹)	Turbine inlet temperature (K)	RTE (%)	Economic indicator
Concentrated solar heat [177]	Solar heat for expansion	1	~300 °C–400 °C	~27.55	\
Concentrated solar heat [179]	CSP power for liquefying air Solar heat for expansion	54	~400 °C	~54.05	PBP: 2.42 years Overall profit: 137.4 \$M
Solar PV & wind power [110]	Solar and wind power for charging LAES	100/3 h	~377 °C	~51.7	LCOE: 150 € MWh ⁻¹ LCOS: 50 € MWh ⁻¹
Solar PV & wind power [140]	Solar and wind power for charging LAES	100/4 h	~1300 °C	~52.7	LCOE: 80–130 € MWh ⁻¹ SB: 5.43 € MWh ⁻¹
Concentrated solar heat & wind power [181]	Solar heat for expansion Wind power for charging LAES	3.9	~60 °C	~45.7%	\
Wind power [47]	Wind power for charging LAES	3	~200 °C	~47.9%	Total profits: k€ 729.2–958.6
Geothermal power [176]	Geothermal power & heat for liquefaction and expansion	12/1 h	~127 °C	LAES: ~47% Overall: ~24.4%	\
Geothermal power [182]	Same as [176]	12/1 h	~127 °C	LAES: ~47% Overall: ~28.4%	\

proposed the integration of LAES with a parabolic trough based concentrated solar power (CSP) system with solar heat stored in a thermal oil at ~300 °C–400 °C. The integrated system was found to be able to provide 30% more output power than the summation of power provided by the CSP and LAES alone. Other studies include the use of other media to store heat from CSP at higher temperatures ranging from 574 °C [178] to 1100 °C [179] for LAES discharging, and for both LAES charging and discharging processes [180].

- *Integration with solar PV* Studies on LAES integration with solar PV have been focused on techno-economic analyses. Legrand *et al* [110] investigated the LCOE of integrating LAES with solar power for the Spanish

power grid. The effects of LAES capacity and renewable ratio (wind power to solar power) were investigated. Their data indicated that the LCOE and LCOS (LCOE without accounting for electricity purchase costs) could be reduced to 150 and 50 € MWh⁻¹, respectively, with a sufficiently higher solar energy penetration in the Spanish power grid. They also evaluated the price arbitrage function of LAES in a future 2030 scenario in Spain with almost 100% renewables (wind + PV) in another study [140]. They found an optimal size of the LAES charging power is about 80% of PV nominal power. Such optimum scenario means a power ratio between charge and discharge is ~0.25 (short daytime charge and long night discharge). Damak *et al* [30] performed an economic analysis on LAES integration with a PV power plant and a cold storage warehouse. Self-sufficiency and sound economics could be achieved at sufficiently high PV generation.

- *Hybrid integration* There have been studies on hybrid renewable integration with LAES; see for example the studies summarised above [25, 140]. Other studies include the integration of wind and solar with LAES [181], in which LAES was mainly charged by wind power, solar heat was used for LAES discharging process, while excess compression heat of LAES is used for domestic hot water. Such a hybrid plant could give a RTE of ~50% and an exergy efficiency of ~46%. Liang *et al* [47] performed a detailed study on the integration of a decoupled LAES plant to a hybrid renewable micro-grid with ~50% of wind power. Their results revealed an optimal energy to power ratio of LAES with ~12 h charging and 6 h discharging for stabilising wind power generation. The major revenue streams included peak shaving (28%), flexibility (21%), operating reserve (20.4%), arbitrage (13.2%), wind firming (~11.4%) and waste heat benefits (6%) [47]. Ji *et al* [181] proposed the use of LAES to store solar and wind energy, and showed, by modelling, the RTE and exergy efficiency are about 45.7% and 44.2%, respectively.
- *Integration with geothermal* Two studies have been found on LAES integration with geothermal power generation. In one of the studies, energy generated from a single flash geothermal plant during off-peak hours is used to produce and store liquid air. LAES power recovery occurs at peak hours using geothermal heat at ~180 °C [176]. The RTE of the LAES was estimated at ~47%, while the overall efficiency of the integrated system was found to be only 24.4%. The other study considered a binary geothermal power plant (6 MW) integrated with an air LFU and a C-ORC (1.4 MW) [182]. The C-ORC was driven by the geothermal heat source (~180 °C). The overall efficiency of the combined system was estimated at ~28.4%. This study also indicated a viable solution for flexible operation of geothermal power plants for peak shaving.

4.2.4. LAES integration with other energy storage technologies

Recent years have also seen reports on the integration of LAES with other storage technologies, including CAES, PTES, and TES. They are summarised in the following.

- Nabat *et al* [127] investigated an integrated LAES system with a thermoelectric generator, a high-temperature thermal energy store, and an ORC. Their techno-economic analyses indicated the system energy and exergy efficiencies at 61.13% and 52.84%, respectively, with a payback period (PBP) of 3.91 years.
- Wu *et al* [128] proposed an integrated system consisting of LAES and a thermochemical energy store. Their techno-economic analyses showed the system-level RTE and energy density at 47.4% and 36.8 kWh m⁻³, respectively, with the PBP and LCOE respectively at ten years and 179–186 \$ MWh⁻¹.
- Farres-Antunez *et al* [183] examined an integrated LAES and PTES system, with the cold reservoir of LAES replaced by a cryogenic HEX with helium from PTES as the HTF. Their thermodynamic analysis indicated a similar RTE of ~60% as the systems operated separately, but with a significantly higher energy density. The study, however, did not include any economic analysis.
- Xu *et al* [178] compared a liquid CO₂ based energy storage (LCES) system and an LAES system in terms of RTE, exergy efficiency, and volumetric energy density. Their results showed higher RTE (45.35%) and exergy efficiency (67.2%) of LCES compared with the data for LAES (37.83% and 45.48% respectively). The energy density of LAES (101.6 kWh m⁻³) is about 6 times higher than that of LCES (18.06 kWh m⁻³).
- Krawczyk *et al* [174] compared a LAES (270 MW, 1080 MWh) and a CAES (290 MW, 1700 MWh) system. Their thermodynamic analyses indicated a major advantage of LAES over CAES in terms of energy density and efficiency. Peng *et al* [46] obtained similar results with an energy density of LAES (40.49 × 10⁴ kJ m⁻³) ~7 times that of CAES.
- Georgiou *et al* [129] compared LAES and PTES by techno-economic analyses. The results indicated a lower power and energy capital cost of LAES, but PTES was found to be more competitive than LAES in terms of LCOS at an electricity purchasing price higher than 0.15 \$ kWh⁻¹.
- Kantharaj *et al* [184] proposed a CAES system with liquid air storage, with an aim to overcome the needs for a pressurized large storage tank and the geological constraint of CAES. They found an efficiency of the hybrid system at about 42%, and concluded that the system was more economical than purely an LAES or a CAES system. Based on the similar concept, Pimm *et al* [185] developed an optimization algorithm and control strategy to determine the optimal operation of a hybrid LAES and CAES system. Their results

indicated that the return on investment could be maximized if the charging time of the hybrid system was higher than 36 h, with 80% of total storage capacity being liquid air at a charge time/discharge time of 2.5:1.

4.2.5. LAES integration with ASU

The published studies of LAES integrated with ASU can be broadly split into two categories: one involves the use of gaseous products, e.g. nitrogen, oxygen, from the ASU; and the other shares the use of ASU components, e.g. compressors and HEXs.

- *The use of ASU gaseous products* There are studies on the use of oxygen from the ASU to combust gaseous fuel for driving gas turbines, and the use of liquid nitrogen from the ASU as the energy storage medium as well as the working fluid for LAES. Both have been shown to enhance power output and efficiency greatly [186–188]. Additionally, part of cold energy from liquid nitrogen can be recovered and reused to separate and condense carbon dioxide at the turbine exhaust, realizing carbon capture without additional energy input. Wang *et al* [109] proposed the use of crude nitrogen from the ASU as the working fluid for LAES, part of compression heat from LAES charging process for the regeneration of ASU absorber (air cleaning unit), and the use of high-purity oxygen product from the ASU sold for additional revenues. The RTE of such a hybrid system was estimated at only ~39%, but the payback period for a 10 MW/80 MWh system could be reduced to three years due to the revenue from arbitrage, high-purity oxygen, and heat supply.
- *The sharing of core components* He *et al* [189] proposed the integration of an ASU with an LAES system, with the compression, cooling, and purification equipment in the ASU system shared with LAES system without affecting the normal operation of the ASU. They found that, when product gas demand of the ASU is lower than 105%, the remaining loads of the air compressors and coolers can be shared by the LAES charging process. During LAES discharging, the evaporation of liquid air occurs in the main HEX of the ASU, providing additional cold energy to the ASU. Their results showed that the RTE of the integrated system could be increased from 46% to 65% when the gas load demand of the ASU varies between 70% and 100%.

5. Perspectives of potential LAES applications

5.1. LAES for power sector

LAES at different scales can provide various services in the power sector, to reap benefits and decarbonize the electrical systems as illustrated in figure 9.

As mentioned earlier, LAES can be integrated with nuclear power plant for peak-shaving and load-shifting, which could lead to an enhanced efficiency and a significantly increased peak load [87]. Khani and Zadeh [191] investigated optimal dispatch of LAES to serve an arbitrage function on a day-ahead and week-ahead electricity market. They showed that weekly dispatches would be more beneficial. Our unpublished experimental work on LAES operating under the so-called SpinGen mode with turbo-expander-generator pre-synchronised showed a response time ~10 s, implying that the LAES could provide at least secondary frequency regulation services (refer to table 10). The LAES can also be integrated with a fast-response storage devices, such as battery or flywheel, to provide full-range frequency regulation services to the power grid [192]. Vecchi *et al* [72, 130] performed a techno-economic analysis on LAES for fast reserve and short term operating reserve services in the UK electricity market. Their results showed a portfolio of financially promising reserve services, but such services were found to affect the RTE of LAES as well. Li *et al* proposed a hybrid system consisting of CAES and battery to serve as back-up for an islanded micro-grid [125]. Their techno-economic analysis indicated clear economic and environmental advantages of the hybrid system over diesel engine for providing black-start function. Such a hybrid system could also work by replacing the CAES with LAES.

5.2. LAES for sector coupling

As summarised in section 4.2, LAES can be integrated with various industrial processes for waste heat/cold energy recovery and utilisation, and hence to enhance system efficiency. LAES can also be applied through sector coupling. An example is the integration with an ammonia synthesis plant, where the exhaust nitrogen from the LAES discharging process can be used to feed ammonia synthesis, as illustrated in figure 10. At off-peak times, the ASU provides nitrogen for both the ammonia synthesis (as a feed gas) and the LAES (as a storage medium). At peak times, the ASU is switched off, and the stored liquid nitrogen in the LAES system is discharged to generate electricity, with the turbine exhaust nitrogen fed to the ammonia synthesis system. As a result, the ASU only consumes off-peak electricity, leading to reduced operating costs. This integrated system can offer several other benefits/synergies:

Figure 9. Applications of energy storage in the power sector. Adapted from [190].

Table 10. Frequency regulation services in the UK market [27, 130, 193].

	Primary Regulation		Secondary Regulation	Tertiary Regulation
	Primary Response	Secondary Response	Fast Reserve	Short Term Operating Reserve
Response time	≤10 s	≤30 s	≤2 min	≤240 min
Minimum sustained period	20 s	30 min	15 min	120 min
Minimum power commitment	1 MW	1 MW	50 MW	3 MW
Minimum delivery rate	—	—	25 MW min ⁻¹	—

Figure 10. Integration of LAES with ammonia synthesis process. Reprinted from [27], Copyright (2021), with permission from Elsevier.

- Electricity generated by the LAES can be used in the ammonia synthesis process;
- The excess reaction heat (~500 °C) of the ammonia synthesis process can be used in the LAES discharging process to enhance power output;
- The integrated system can be driven by renewable energy (solar or wind), achieving ‘Green ammonia’ production, with the LAES for time-shifting of renewable energy.

Other examples of applications of LAES for sector coupling include:

Table 11. The comparison of power services and sector coupling capability of LAES with other storage technologies.

Storage systems	Response time	Power services capability [198, 199]	Sector coupling capability [200]
LAES	min [16, 17]	Energy arbitrage, peak shaving, load following, black start, spinning reserve, transmission deferral, intermittent RES	Power sector Cooling sector Heating sector Renewable integration Waste heat integration Waste cold integration
PHS	min [19]	Time shifting, supply reserve, frequency control, and non-spinning reserve, black start	Power sector Water sector Renewable integration
CAES	min [19]	Frequency and voltage control, peak shaving, load shifting, and intermittent RES, black start	Power sector Heating sector Waste heat integration Renewable integration
Flow battery (Vanadium redox)	<sec [19]	Spinning reserve, frequency control, voltage support, load shifting, power quality, black start	Power sector Transport sector Renewable integration
Hydrogen storage coupled with fuel cell	< sec [20] s–min [19]	Power quality, backup power, time shifting, non-spinning reserve, frequency control, black start	Power sector Transport sector Heating sector Gas sector Renewable integration Waste heat integration

- *Carbon capture* Air purification is essential for the LAES to remove the water vapour, carbon dioxide (CO₂), hydrocarbons, and particulates. The CO₂ and hydrocarbon are greenhouse gases [194], and hence the LAES offers an opportunity for direct carbon capture without adding much costs [195].
- *Offshore renewable energy (ORE) transmission* LAES could offer onshore and ORE storage and transmission functions when its charging and discharging processes are separately located [196]. Figure 11 shows an

example of the technology for storing ORE [197]. In such a system, liquid air is produced at an off-shore site, which is transported by current shipping infrastructure, and stored at an onshore-site. In this way, offshore transmission lines and electrical infrastructure can be avoided, thus, increases the flexibility of LAES system.

In terms of the power services and sector coupling capability of LAES systems, table 11 shows a comparison with other storage technologies.

6. Conclusions

This article provides a comprehensive review on LAES. It differs from previous reviews published in recent years, particularly the following aspects of LAES: dynamic simulation and optimisation, key components for LAES, LAES applications through integration, and unified economic and cost models for LAES components. The review covers the following aspects:

- Principle, development history and current deployment status;
- Key components for LAES;
- Device and system-scale modelling, including thermodynamic modelling, dynamic modelling and economic modelling;
- Techno-economic analysis of both stand-alone and integrated LAES systems;
- LAES systems with and without compression heat utilization, and integrated LAES systems with external heat and cold sources, renewables, ASU and other storage technologies;
- Potential applications of LAES in power sector and through sector coupling.

The review also indicates several areas of LAES for future research and development, including dynamic characteristics of whole LAES system integrated with renewables and end users; thermo-economic and dynamic optimization of stand-alone LAES and integrated systems; and experimental study on commercial LAES systems.

Data availability statement

All data that support the findings of this study are included within the article (and any supplementary files).

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